

IDENTIFY THE CRITICAL TO ENHANCE THE ENVIRONMENTAL PERFORMANCE OF SME OF PAKISTAN. DEMYSTIFYING THE ROLE OF GREEN INNOVATION PERFORMANCE

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Abstract

The notion of environmental performance in Pakistani textiles is still far from satisfactory. Thus, based on the service dominating logic theory, this study investigates how green value co-creation (GVCC) affects green environmental performance (EP) for Pakistani green textiles and ascertains how green innovation (GI) plays a mediating function. Purposive sampling was the method utilized to collect data from 446 textile samples generated in Pakistan. The questionnaires were given to executives in Pakistan's Multan Industrial Zone who worked in the textile industry. The research was carried out by use of structural equation modeling employing partial least squares and SPSS. According to our research, green innovation and green environmental performance are both enhanced through green value co-creation. In addition to facilitating green value co-creation and green environmental performance, green innovation mediates this interplay. There will be extensive discussion of the results' theoretical and practical implications.

Introduction

Manufacturing companies are essential to the expansion of the economy in the contemporary world, but they also negatively affect society and the environment (Guo et al., 2020). The economy's rapid expansion is making environmental degradation, hefty industrial waste, and excessive carbon emissions worse every day. In addition to being harmful to civilization, environmental deterioration has become a serious hazard to human existence (Karimi Takalo et al., 2021). The environment has become a top priority for corporations as knowledge and technology advance. Customers' shifting preferences for environmentally friendly goods are putting more and more pressure on businesses to take environmental performance into account (Latif et al., 2020; Singh et al., 2022). Furthermore, governments, society, customers, and international organizations have all pushed businesses to give environmental performance improvement top priority (Akhtar et al., 2024). Communities' intents shift in favor of environmentally friendly products as a result. This change in emphasis has made it more necessary for SMEs to confront environmental challenges and learn environmental protection (de Sousa et al., 2020).

To some extent, industrial environmental contamination has been controlled in developed nations. However, climate change, hazardous materials, resource depletion, air pollution, and chemical waste continue to be major problems for manufacturing firms in developing nations (Lopes de Sousa Jabbour et al., 2020). Pakistan is a developing nation where SMEs account for 90% of all businesses and 40% of the GDP. Because they can adjust to change faster than big businesses, SMEs have a lot of promise for sustained development, according to research. Despite this promise, their capacity to effect constructive change has been hampered by a lack of information, R&D, and financial resources (Science et al., 2022). Due to their production processes and marketing strategies, Pakistani small and medium-sized textile made-up (SMEs) involved in manufacturing contribute to environmental pollution and harm (Akhtar et al., 2024). As a result, the manufacturing sector, particularly SMEs, must pay attention to environmental management programs, make environmental decisions, and fight to promote green innovation (Musaad O et al., 2020). One of the key requirements for industry is the use of green innovation and environmental performance to guarantee sustainable growth (Jermisittiparsert, 2021).

Green innovation may help SMEs meet changing customer needs in the current business environment (Machado et al., 2020). Green innovation is essential and distinctive for environmental consumer concerns (Musaad O et al., 2020). Green innovation emerged when customers learned about environmental rules (Leoncini et al., 2016). This is what Judge and Douglas (1998) mean when they say that environmental performance is "a firm's ability to meet and exceed society's environmental expectations. ." There are several studies that have looked at the financial and economic performance of Pakistani SMEs. Some assess it in terms of both economic and green performance (Asiaei et al., 2022). However, there aren't many studies that examine how businesses convert their environmental practices, skills, and plans into

environmental performance and pinpoint the vital resources they must enhance (Yahya et al., 2024).

Over the last decade, scholars have focused on green innovation and environmental performance due to environmental issues, resource depletion, and stress (Kawai et al., 2018). SMEs encounter various hurdles in green innovation because they lack green dynamic skills, green processes, and green value co-creation. Clear research is required to assess how green value co-creation influences SME green innovation (Yousaf, 2021). Prior research has examined value creation and value co-creation; however, there hasn't been much focus on integrating environmental solutions into value co-creation. However, value co-creation may be used to develop unique environmental solutions (Chang, 2019). In order to enhance VCC, consumers may participate in the manufacturing and consumption stages of the process, which is known as "green value co-creation" (Guo et al., 2020).

The subject of how value co-creation processes support green innovation has received more attention in the literature than the relationship between GVCC and GI to yet (Yousaf, 2021). Due to system characteristics and technological uncertainties, prior research measured organizational collaboration for green innovation implementation and interfirm cooperation with green innovation (Burki & Dahlstrom, 2017). Additionally, knowledge sharing involved integrating internal and external knowledge (Dangelico, 2016). Very little research has examined the mediating and impact of green value co-creation and green innovation on environmental performance.

By quantifying the direct and indirect effects of green value co-creation on environmental performance—both of which have not previously been examined in the literature—our research closes this gap. Studying SMEs and their significance for environmental performance is emphasized by (Asiaei et al., 2021). This study's main goal was to assess the environmental performance of Pakistani textile-based SMEs, since this industry often disregards environmental issues.

This work provides many important contributions to the field. The relationship between green value co-creation and the environmental performance of textile-based SMEs in Pakistan is examined because researchers have suggested investigating the mechanisms of this relationship (Yousaf, 2021). This study also examines green value co-creation, co-production, and use to measure environmental performance directly and through green innovation, which has not been studied in Pakistani SMEs (Farzaneh et al., 2022).

Literature Review

Environmental Performance

" Judge and Douglas (1998) define environmental performance as a firm's ability to meet and surpass society's environmental expectations. An organization's capacity to lower energy use, air emissions, hazardous material use, material utilization, and environmental standard compliance (Laosirihongthong et al., 2013). Environmental performance is influenced by the company's capacity to reduce emissions and waste production, as well as hazardous and toxic chemicals and environmental occurrences (Asadi et al., 2020). Environmental performance, according to Elkington (1997), is about preventing resource exploitation and minimizing environmental harm. According to Pipatprapa et al. (2018), green performance is the extent to which a company's operations are environmentally friendly.

Green Value Co Creation

Value co-creation is the process by which a business and its stakeholders work together for production or consumption purposes at one or more stages. It alludes to the active exchange of ideas and expertise in order to produce creative solutions. The Service-Dominant (S-D) Logic suggests that all stakeholders contribute to the development of value rather than only the corporation (Vargo & Lusch, 2014).

Value co-creation is a business approach that promotes and encourages a company's engagement in customer expectations and value to satisfy those wants. It is often stated from the perspective of the consumer. Value co-creation by enterprises makes it easier for customers to acquire what they desire (Pargar et al., 2019). Environmental ideas shared between a company and its customers are called "green value co-creation." This interaction may include consumers in production and consumption to promote value co-creation (Chou et al., 2022; Guo et al., 2020). Innovative concepts that actively communicate environmental ideas with partners in one or more production or consumption phases can develop green values (Yousaf, 2021).

This research introduces "green value co-creation," using the term from (Ranjan & Read, 2016). Green value co-creation involves a corporation and its partners exchanging environmental ideas and participating in production or consumption to produce value. This research divides green value co-creation into green co-production and green value-in-use (Ranjan & Read, 2016). The practice of firms working together to produce green innovation is known as "green co-production." Green co-production consists of three components: engagement, equality, and knowledge exchange. Sharing knowledge between a business and its partners co-creates value and increases competency throughout the development process. When it comes to co-creation activities, equity is the readiness to share power with partners. The interface between a business and its partners is called interaction. The green co-production process is just one aspect of green value-in-use. Customer or business experiences learning to use, mend, and maintain green product innovation is called "green value-in-use." Green value-in-use includes experience, customisation, and connections (Chang, 2019).

Experience is seen as a business that creates value for its partners. Through experience in usage, partners co-create value even during the trial stage (Edvardsson et al., 2022). The distinctiveness of the co-creation process is what is meant by personalization. Active communication and interaction between businesses constitute a connection. In practice, green value is a reciprocal relationship between a business and its partners.

Green Innovation

Green innovation may help SMEs meet changing customer needs in the current business environment (Machado et al., 2020). Green innovation is essential and distinctive for environmental consumer concerns (Musaad O et al., 2020). Green innovation emerged when customers learned about environmental rules (Leoncini et al., 2016). Manufacturing companies adopt green innovation measures to reduce their operational systems' environmental impact. Green innovation helps firms improve their services, technology, and operations for green management (Zhang and Liang 2012). Green innovation improves firms' products and processes to reduce waste, pollution, energy use, etc. Green innovation is essential yet difficult.

Green Value Co Creation and Environmental Performance

Innovations that actively communicate environmental concepts with partners in one or more production or consumption phases to jointly produce green values are called "green value co-creation" (Chang, 2019; Yousaf, 2021). The "propensity for greening" idea involves customers in logistical tasks to improve environmental performance. Venus Lun et al. (2015). The mediating role of green innovation was explored to assess the influence of green intellectual capital on economics and green performance (C. H. Wang & Juo, 2021). The management is strongly advised to urge partners to collaborate in order to seize chances that they would not have been able to explore on their own. All value co-creation is positively correlated with the sustainable performance of logistic service providers, according to research by Fernando and Chukai (2018) that examines value co-creation and the effect of goods and services taxes on sustainable logistic performance (SLP). In order to achieve the environmental goals, the research is unusual in that it involves the client in their operations. Therefore, we have suggested in this research that

H1: Green value co creation has positive impact on environmental performance.

Green Value Co Creation and Green Innovation

Environmental ideas shared between a company and its customers are called "green value co-creation." Innovative organizations must adopt green practices. However, organizational innovation requires green practices (Huang & Li, 2017). The organization and its clients may improve capabilities and co-create value for innovation via the exchange of information throughout the development process (Havemo, 2018). Using its two-dimensional green co-production and green value in use, we have quantified green value co-creation. When green innovation is still being developed, green co-production serves as a method of cooperation between businesses and consumers (Kazadi et al., 2016). Businesses and consumers have different green goals, but they are nonetheless focused on improving their co-production

process since it incorporates their stakeholder norms, ethical standards, and self-interest—all of which are factors that influence green innovation (Chiou & Droge, 2006). The organization and its clients may improve capabilities and co-create value for innovation via the exchange of information throughout the development process (Havemo, 2018). When used, "green value" refers to methods and practices that are beneficial to the environment. To meet the goals of green innovation, businesses must cultivate green value cocreation and demonstrate enthusiasm in using green value (Asadi et al., 2020). In order to achieve green innovation, the organization develops value co-creation via the use of environmentally friendly materials in product manufacturing, which generates consumer value (Kohler et al., 2011). However, there aren't many studies that quantify the co-creation of green value as a key factor influencing environmental performance and green innovation. We contend in this research that green innovation is predicted by green value co-creation. It lessens the impact on the environment while enhancing the businesses' practices, products, and procedures (Yook et al., 2018).

Hence, we proposed that: H2 Green value co creation has significant and positive relationship with green innovation

Green Innovation And Environmental Performance

GI helps businesses, organizations, and society achieve environmental sustainability and boosts economic performance (Chu et al., 2019). Green innovation is needed for environmental management (Chen, 2008). Creating new products and technologies to reduce environmental issues like pollution and resource extraction is called "green innovation" or "eco innovation" (Castellacci & Lie, 2017). Enhancing the functionality of goods and services for consumers and clients is the ultimate aim of product/service innovation (Albort-Morant et al., 2018). According to another research, green innovation may improve an organization's performance (Olson, 2014). Lower the rate of pollution while gaining an edge over competitors (Aguilera-Caracuel & Ortiz-de-Mandojana, 2013). Many towns and organizations have turned to GI as a means of achieving both economic development and environmental preservation (Karimi Takalo et al., 2021). Manufacturing companies adopt green innovation measures to reduce their operational systems' environmental impact. Green innovation helps firms improve their services, technology, and operations for green management (Zhang and Liang 2012). GI is the enhancement of businesses' goods and methods to apply environmental management systems via waste reduction, pollution control, energy conservation, etc. Achieving green innovation is a crucial yet challenging and intricate endeavor. Therefore, we suggested that :H3 Green innovation has positive impact on environmental performance

Mediating Role Of Green Innovation Between Green Value Co Creation And Environmental Performance

Research by C. H. Wang and Juo (2021), green innovation mediates economic-green performance-green intellectual capital. Leaders should examine their impact on performance. Managers should urge partners to cooperate to maximize opportunities. The study found that green value co-creation improves the mediating relationship between green innovation, green

dynamic capability, and green practices (Yousaf, 2021). According to Yousaf (2021), the research has focused more on value co-creation approaches improving GI than GVCC and GI. Our research has focused on green innovation and green value co-creation as major factors affecting environmental performance.

Hence, we proposed that: H4 green innovation mediate the relationship between green value co creation and environmental performance.

Methodology

Methods of research This study was developed utilizing a quantitative technique and is empirically interpretive in character. PLS-SEM was used to test the study's assumptions, while SmartPLS 3.0 was employed for analysis. Because it is suitable for the explanatory character of the present study, this approach was used (Hair et al., 2010). Furthermore, PLS should be used when the model is finished and the sample size is minimal, according to Hair et al. (2014). So, PLS-SEM should be considered as it is suitable for determining the following causes, according to Chin (1998a, b). First, an ordinary distributional assumption is not necessary for PLS-SEM. Second, it handles several independent and dependent variables at once with great success. Third, PLS-SEM can handle issues with multicollinearity between independent variables and very small sample sizes. Three subsections comprise this technique section: measurements for constructs, data and sample size, and data analysis.

Fig:1 Research Framework

Data and Sample Size

In order to gather answers for analysis, a questionnaire was sent to textile SMEs in Multan City, Pakistan. Information was gathered from Pakistan's Multan city. Three distinct industries of textile manufacturing SMEs were targeted inside the Multan zone: the production of clothing, towels, and spinning and weaving. Due to their abundance and primary role in environmental contamination, these industries were selected for the data sample. The Chamber of Commerce and Industry provided the list of SMEs in these industries. In light of this, we addressed our

questionnaire to 750 textile manufacturing SMEs, focusing on both registered and unregistered SMEs as our target industrial zones. This study used random sampling. Random sampling was considered optimal since every unit has an equal probability of being picked (Secker et al., 1995). Yamane's (1967), and 446 of the 470 completed questionnaires were determined to be usable. This amounts to 59.5 percent, which is regarded as an effective response rate. The top and middle management of textile-made SMEs in Multan, Pakistan, who actively participate in the SME's strategic decision-making, were the study's target group. Pakistani small and medium-sized textile manufacturing businesses are included in our analysis. The partner (owner), general manager, chief marketing manager, chief production manager, chief operation manager, chief financing manager, and managers involved in the decision-making process of the textile sector of SME in Pakistan were sent questionnaires because they have extensive and first-hand knowledge of green practices and the current state of the firm.

Measures for Constructs

We used existing study scales to examine factors. The questions were collated and placed on a 5-point Likert scale, with 1 indicating severe disagreement and 5 strongly agreeing. Content validity has been shown using modified measurements from previous studies (Trochim 2016). Four items changed from the (Z. Han & Huo, 2020) and (Li, 2022) scales are used to test the EP, eight items modified from (Chen et al., 2006) are used to measure GI, and thirteen items modified from (C. H. Chang, 2019; Ranjan & Read, 2016; H. H. Tian et al., 2022) are used to test the GVCC.

Data Analysis

The measuring of the model and the testing of the association between latent variables are the two processes necessary to use PLS-SEM. Prior to calculating the model's structural connection, these two procedures were taken to guarantee the validity and reliability of the measurements. The measuring of the model and the testing of the association between latent variables are the two processes necessary to use PLS-SEM. Prior to calculating the model's structural connection, these two procedures were taken to guarantee the validity and reliability of the measurements.

Measurement Model Results

For each research, a model's validity and reliability must be verified. This research evaluated the validity and reliability in a number of ways. For each item, factor loadings more than 0.5 are deemed acceptable, while factor loadings greater than 0.7 are deemed desirable, in accordance with the general guideline established by Hair et al. (2010). Item dependability was validated since all of the items in the current investigation had item loadings greater than 0.5. Similarly, according to the general criterion of Hair et al. (2014), composite reliability (CR) should exceed 0.7. This study found that all constructs had CR more than 0.7 and the model's internal reliability (an alternative to Cronbach's α) above 0.7, satisfying the rule of thumb. Convergent validity was tested using the average variance extracted (AVE); Fornell and Larcker (1981) need all constructs' AVEs to be more than 0.5, which this study did. Figure 2 and Table I give specifics on the measuring methodology and its assessment, respectively. Additionally, each

variable's descriptive statistics are included in Table II. Descriptive statistical data show that GI (mean 3.096), EP (mean 2.832), and GVCC (mean 2.594). To verify discriminant validity, two methods were evaluated. The first test was cross-loading, which requires that a construct's indicator loading be greater than the loadings of other constructs (Hair et al., 2014). Table III shows that cross-loading in this model confirmed discriminant validity. Second, Fornell and Larcker's (1981) criteria were utilized, which require each construct's square root of the AVE to be bigger than its inter-correlation with other constructs in the model. Discriminant validity was found in the present model (Table IV). The first two discriminant validity detection approaches were inaccurate (Henseler et al., 2015).

Assessment of the Structural Model

After establishing the veracity of the findings of the measurement of the model, the structural model was next examined. In this research, the model explains 50.3 percent of the variation in green innovation ($R^2 = 0.503$) and 51.5 percent of the variance in environmental performance ($R^2 = 0.515$). Stone-Geisser Q^2 (cross-validated redundancy) was used to evaluate the model's ability to predict latent component indicators, per Stone (1974) and Geisser (1975). This approach is useful for evaluating model fit assessments. The projected relevance was calculated using SmartPLS3 blindfolding. Chin (2010) defines predictive significance as a Q^2 value greater than 0. The Q^2 value of 0.412, which is more than 0, indicates that this model is predictively relevant.

Table I: Measurement Model Evaluation

Items Loadings, Average Variance Extracted and Composite Reliability

Constructs	Items	Loadings	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
Green value creation (GVCC)	GCP1	0.823	0.958	0.963	0.666
	GCP2	0.858			
	GCP3	0.850			
	GCP4	0.878			
	GCP5	0.744			
	GCP6	0.775			
	GVIU1	0.746			
	GVIU2	0.856			
	GVIU3	0.861			
	GVIU4	0.880			
	GVIU5	0.785			
	GVIU6	0.794			
	GVIU7	0.727			

Environmental performance (EP)	ENV 1	0.851	0.809	0.874	0.635
	ENV2	0.874			
	ENV3	0.892			
	ENV4	0.894			
Green Innovation (GI)	GI1	0.769	0.89	0.911	0.565
	GI2	0.836			
	GI3	0.788			
	GI4	0.851			
	GI5	0.889			
	GI6	0.738			
	GI7	0.877			
	GI8	0.729			

Results and Discussion

Researchers studying green innovation and environmental challenges have focused a lot of emphasis on the growing environmental deterioration. These worries are now putting a lot of pressure on manufacturers worldwide. Despite this fact, very few SMEs in Pakistan are taking environmental concerns into account while developing their business plans. The purpose of this research was to identify the key determinants of green innovation uptake in Pakistani SMEs. H1, H2, and H3 are supported by the study's results (see Table VI).

Table II: *Results Of Descriptive Statistics*

Construct	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Dev
GVCCmean	446	1.00	5.00	2.5942	0.87201
EPmean	446	1.00	5.00	2.8330	0.91928
GImean	446	1.00	5.00	3.0961	0.91579

In accordance with earlier research (Weng et al., 2025), the results of hypothesis H3 demonstrate that green innovation practices have positive and significant effects on environmental performance ($\beta = 0.642$ $t = 26.506$ $p = 0.000$), suggesting that a company that practices green innovation will in fact see improved environmental performance. Businesses may meet industry and regulatory standards, reduce waste and pollution, save the environment, and boost their competitiveness all at once by putting green innovation strategies into practice.

Table III: *Cross-Loading Test For Discriminant Validity*

	EP	GI	GVCC
EP1	0.851	0.284	0.183
EP2	0.874	0.248	0.196
EP3	0.892	0.647	-0.002
EP4	0.894	0.632	-0.009
GI1	0.428	0.769	-0.085
GI2	0.466	0.836	-0.023
GI3	0.457	0.788	-0.084
GI4	0.497	0.851	-0.071
GI5	0.334	0.889	-0.089
GI6	0.39	0.738	-0.027
GI7	0.31	0.877	0.132
GI8	0.718	0.729	-0.042
GVCP1	0.08	-0.011	0.823
GVCP2	0.034	-0.046	0.858
GVCP3	0.023	-0.069	0.850
GVCP4	0.066	-0.065	0.878
GVCP5	0.046	-0.036	0.744
GVCP6	0.07	-0.024	0.775
GVIU1	0.062	-0.077	0.746
GVIU2	0.06	-0.026	0.856
GVIU3	0.051	-0.064	0.861
GVIU4	0.075	-0.063	0.880
GVIU5	0.014	-0.036	0.785
GVIU6	0.059	-0.011	0.794
GVIU7	0.043	-0.016	0.727

Table IV: *Fornell And Larcker's Criterion Test For Discriminant Validity*

	EP	GI	GVCC
EP	0.786		
GI	0.636	0.752	
GVCC	0.069	-0.056	0.815

By using these strategies, they may also enhance their company's reputation and draw in more clients. However, our findings imply that "going green" is not only a means for businesses to comply with laws; they can also utilize green innovation to proactively establish new guidelines for improving and maintaining their performance and capabilities. Increasing a business's capability for green innovation might provide managers a new tactical tool.

Table VI: *Path Coefficient And Hypothesis Testing*

Sr #	Hypothesis	Std β	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
H1	GVCC \rightarrow EP	0.405	0.405	0.025	15.566	0
H2	GVCC \rightarrow GI	0.556	0.553	0.028	21.864	0
H3	GI \rightarrow EP	0.642	0.645	0.024	26.506	0
H4	GVCC \rightarrow GI \rightarrow EP	0.336	0.335	0.025	13.853	0

Hypothesis H4 only shows a direct link between green value co-creation and green environmental protection, extending the preceding research on green innovation's mediation role. GVCC is only connected to environmental performance via green innovation, demonstrating that green innovation completely mediates the relationship. SME operations must include eco-friendly concepts. Businesses may struggle to penetrate new markets due to green initiative environmental regulations (Barrett, 1991). According to Ranjan and Read (2016), GVCC enterprises collaborate to produce value across production and consumption. This direct or indirect partnership may include environmental concepts and involvement in production or consumption. Value co-creation is the key to an organization's success in providing products and services. Rehman & Siddiqui (2023) also argue that ecological methods boost textile brand image. They said government policies that give financial incentives, technical resources, pilot projects, and training programs encourage SMEs to adopt green practices. SMEs also adopt green innovation due to banks' easy financing programs and government subsidies (EIO, 2011; Hojnik and Ruzzier, 2016).

The Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) at the Ministry of Climate Change helps Pakistani SMEs implement green practices. Pakistan's EPA promotes sustainable development, environmental preservation, conservation, rehabilitation, and improvement in addition to pollution management. This organization also wants to provide firms cutting-edge pollution avoidance technology at the provincial level. Pakistan's EPA advises the Federal Government on fiscal and budgetary strategies, programs, and initiatives to meet environmental goals.

Pakistan's EPA gives incentives, awards, prizes, subsidies, tax exemptions, refunds, and depreciation allowances to SMEs for green practices. It also charges polluting firms taxes, fines, and other fees. Regulators encourage SMEs to adopt green innovation since failing to comply with environmental laws may cost businesses a lot (Berrone et al., 2013).

Conclusion Policy Implications

This study, which expands on Vallaster and Von Wallpach (2013), found that customers choose organizations that consider their demands and have a value co-creation process. To link green practices, innovation, and environmental performance, green value co-creation is necessary. This study linked environmental issues to business problems to help practical management focus on green innovation via green practices, dynamic capacities, and value co-creation. Practical management must communicate their green practices to adapt to green changes. Management should consider stakeholder expectations for "Green Business & Green Products" in practice. This study suggests that environmental performance and management should have these abilities because green value co-creation inspires green innovation. The study's focus on green innovation as a mediator enhances practical management. Businesses depend on many customers, and customer choices affect profitability. Managers must leverage the value chain to provide value for consumers. They will be more excited about value co-creations started using green ways.

Limitations and Future Research

This study evaluated assumptions in Pakistan using a cross-sectional survey; longitudinal surveys in other developing countries may provide different results. This study solely examined manufacturing SMEs; services and non-manufacturing SMEs must be studied to fully understand this important topic.

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